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Subjective Well-being (SWB) among School and College Teachers: A Comparative Study

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ABSTRACT

Teachers are the important guides of human being. That's why it is very important that they remain mentally and physically healthy. In this study, an attempt has been made to measure the Subjective Well-being of the teachers working in different Schools and Colleges of Ranchi district. It was aimed to measure the Subjective Well-being of the teachers and to see the difference in levels of Subjective Well-being between male and female as well as between the teachers working in Schools and Colleges. The study also aimed to see the impact of gender and institutional affiliation on Subjective Well-being. Data were collected using Personal Data Questionnaire and Subjective Well-being Inventory (Thakur, G. P. and Singh, R. N. 2005) from 50 male and 50 female teachers of various schools and colleges. A 2X2 factorial design was adopted and stratification was made on the basis of gender and institutional affiliation for this study. Statistical techniques, such as Mean, SD, t-ratio and ANOVA were applied for the analysis of the data. The results revealed that all the teachers had a high level of Subjective Well-being. The same trend was visible in different sample subgroups and in dimensions-wise scores also. No significant difference was observed between male and female teachers but there existed a significant difference between School teachers and College teachers on Subjective Well-being. ANOVA analysis revealed that gender and institutional affiliation had significant impact on Subjective Well-being, but the interaction of both was found insignificant.

Keywords: *Subjective Well-being, college teachers, Ranchi, positive psychology*

Since last two decades, from the inception of Positive Psychology, the study of happiness and other positive attributes of human kind have attracted the psychologists very much and several studies are being conducted on these issues. The concept of Subjective Well-being is

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important one among the positive attributes of human kind. Subjective Well-being is considered as synonym of happiness. According to Diener, (1984); (2000); Diener et. al., (2009), the subjective evaluation of one's physical and mental wellness may be termed as Subjective Well-being. It emphasizes on the subjective report of one's well being. Not only people of different culture, but within the same culture, people possess individualistic approach while defining their well being or happiness. Keeping this in mind the concept of Subjective Well-being has been coined to define the people's happiness in more particular way. Diener (1984); (2000); Diener et. al. (2009) are of view that "... Well-being is the subjective evaluation of one's current status of well spring in the world".

Therefore, Diener defines Subjective Well-being as "a combination of positive affect (in absence of negative affect) and general life satisfaction".

Well being involves our feeling of pleasure and our view point towards the rewards of our life. Thus, the subjective report of one's life satisfaction or happiness is termed as Subjective Well-being.

Although, this Subjective Well-being is personal, yet certain determinants have been identified and decided by the researchers. Diener and Diener (1995) examined the satisfaction or well being of students of 31 nations. They found that family and wealth, marital status and quality of marital life, sound mental health and good social relationships are the important correlates of Subjective Well-being. While deciding a model for happiness Lyubomirsky et al. (2005) are of opinion that persons happiness is determined by three factors, Festally genetics accounted for 50% of population variance fo happiness, secondly, life circumstances (both good and bad) and lastly, the intentional activity (attempts at healthy living and positive change) accounted for 10% and 40% of the population variance for happiness".

Snyder, C.R. et al opined that "Love" "work" and "play" are the three Life Enhancement Strategies. Being happy is the ultimate goal of common individual. Keeping this in mind the present study has been conceived to gauge the Subjective Well-being of school and college teachers. As the teacher's happiness effects their job, creation of knowledge and imparting quality education, the study endeavors to measure their important psychological trait.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the available literature of well-being and happiness, there are numerous studies. It is one of the major subject matter of Positive Psychology. Some of studies reviewed so far may be presented as follows. These studies are from India as well as from abroad.

Salimiradi, F. and Srimathi, N. L. (2016) conducted a study to find out the relationship between Occupational self-efficacy and psychological well-being among teachers in the city of Mysore, India. The results revealed that high self-efficacy and high psychological well-being were positively related. No significant effect of gender was ovserved on occupational self-efficacy and psychological well-being. This study finds out an important correlate of Subjective Well-being that is self-efficacy.

Stanculescu, E. (2014) explored psychological predictors and mediators of teacher's subjective well-being. The findings of this study enhanced the understanding of personal factors associated with teacher's subjective well-being. Subjective well-being promote school psychologists' interventions for better school teaching performance.

Wangsoyoung, H. (2014) conducted a study to investigate the relationships between self-differentiation, family origin, ego-resiliency, and psychological well-being among pre-service early childhood teachers. It was found that the psychological well-being was positively correlated with almost all aspects of self-differentiation.

Chan, D. W. (2012) explored the relationship between gratitude and forgiveness and psychological well-being among teachers. The results revealed that gratitude and forgiveness correlated remarkably with each other as well as with meaningful-life orientation and psychological well-being.

Chattu, V. K. et al. (2020) conducted a study on 535 health professionals ie. students of Medicines and Dentistry to explore the predictives of Subjective Well-being. The results revealed significant difference among students of different types of schools and their academic performances with respect to their Subjective Well-being and self perceived successes. Academic performance was greatly influenced by the positive and negative experiences. It was also found that Subjective Well-being and academic performance were highly positively correlated with each other and was an important aspect of a student's academic life. Male and female participants did not differ on all the three variables, where as family type, marital status, nationality, age and ethnicity were found to be significant predictors of subjective well-being.

In a study entitled 'An Analysis of the Relationship between Teachers Subjective Well-being and their Occupational Resilience, Cetin, A. (2019) attempted to identify the perception levels regarding Subjective Well-being of the teachers working at school within the province of Sanliurfa in Turkeye

and explored its relationship with their Occupational Resilience. A sample of 346 teachers, divided into 163 women and 183 men during the academic year 2017-2018, was selected for the study. Results revealed a high degree of Subjective Well-being and Occupational Resilience among the teachers. Subjective Well-being was found to be a significant predictor of Occupational Resilience.

Chatterjee, S. and Jethwari, J. (2020) conducted a study to find out the relationship between Mindful Self-care and Subjective Well-being among college students and working professionals. A sample of 200 adults was selected and Mindful Self-Care Scale (MSCS,2018) by Cook-Cottone and Guyker and Subjective Well-being Inventory (1992) by Nagpal and Sell were used to collect the data. There was no significant difference between the two population groups. There was strong positive correlation between Mindful Self-care and Subjective Well-being.

METHODOLOGY

The present study has been conducted following a specific methodology, which may be described as follows:

Objectives of the Study

The present study has been conceived with the following objectives. The study was aimed to:

- To measure the extent of Subjective Well-being of teachers.
- To see the gender difference in Subjective Well-being among teachers.
- To see the difference between school teachers and college teachers on Subjective Well-being.
- To find out the impact of gender and institutional affiliation on Subjective Well-being.

Hypotheses

In pursuance of the above objectives following hypothesis have been formulated:

- The level of Subjective Well-being among teachers will be high.
- The level of Subjective Well-being will vary among various sample groups.
- There will be significant difference between male and female teachers on Subjective Well-being.
- There will be significant difference between school-teachers and college-teacher on Subjective Well-being.
- There will be significant impact of gender and institutional affiliation on Subjective Well-being.
- Selection of the sample

The selection of sample was based on stratified random sampling technique. The stratification was based on gender (male/female) and institutional affiliation (school/college). There were 4 sample sub groups based on 2x2 factorial design and for each sub group 25 cases were selected randomly. Total 50 school and 50 college teachers were selected for the study. The sample design has been presented in Table-1.

Gender	School Teachers	College Teachers	Total
Male	25	25	50
Female	25	25	50
Total	50	50	100

Tools used in the Study

The data of the present study was collected using following tools:

- **Personal Data Questionnaire:** A personal data questionnaire was prepared for collecting personal information about the teachers such as Name of the teachers, Age, Gender, Educational Qualification Name of the schools/colleges, Subject they taught and Total years of teaching experience etc.
- **Subjective Well-being Inventory:** Subjective Well-being Inventory (SWBI) is developed by Thakur, G. P. and Singh, R N. (2005). This inventory had 40 items accompanied by three alternative responses but with varied nomenclature viz, very much often, very good, sometimes, satisfactory, somewhat not often and probably not. The scale consisted of 19 positive and 21 negative both types of items. It provided scores for five different dimensions of SWB- Happiness (12 items), Coping (8 items), Optimism (7 items), Physical Health (6 items) and Social Satisfaction (7 items) Global scores on Subjective Well-being is calculated by adding the scores obtained on all the dimensions.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The data of the present study was analysed using MS Excel and PAST software. The main findings in pursuance of the aims and objectives may be presented are as follows:

Levels of Subjective Well-being among Teachers

To find out the level of Subjective Well-being mean scores have been calculated. The obtained scores have been categorized into three levels- Low, Average and High. The range of the scale of Subjective Well-being Inventory is 1-120. It has been divided into three levels 1-40 (0%-33%) (Low level of SWB), 41-80 (34%-67%) (Average level of SWB) and 81-120 (68%-100%) (High level of SWB).

The mean scores on Subjective Well-being and their interpretations on the total scale and dimension-wise have been presented in Table 2. It reveals that the total sample has obtained a mean score of 88.18 (73.48%), indicating high level of Subjective Well-being among the teachers. The percentage of score obtained on the dimensions and on total scale indicates high level of Subjective Well-being among the sample. However, maximum percentage of score was obtained on Optimism following Happiness, Social Satisfaction, Health and lastly on Coping.

The findings of the study suggest that all the five dimensions produced high level of Subjective Well-being among the teachers. Thus, the hypothesis that the level of Subjective Well-being of School and College Teachers will be high is accepted here.

Table 2

Levels of Subjective Well-being of Teachers (N=100)

Dimensions of Subjective Well-being	Range of the Scales	Mean Scores	Percentage of Mean Scores	Interpretation
Happiness (HA)	1-36	26.68	74.11%	High
Coping (CO)	1-24	17.14	71.42%	High
Optimism (OP)	1-21	15.82	75.33%	High
Health (HE)	1-18	13.15	73.05%	High
Social Satisfaction (SS)	1-21	15.4	73.33%	High
Total	1-120	88.18	73.48%	High

Level of Subjective Well-being among Various Sample Groups

The mean scores on Subjective Well-being and their interpretations on the total sample and different sample sub groups have been presented in Table 3. It reveals that the total sample has obtained a mean score of 88.18 (73.48%), the male teachers has obtained a mean score of 90.08 (75.06%), the female teachers has obtained a mean score of 86.28 (71.9%), School teachers have obtained a mean score of 94.66 (78.88%) and college teachers has obtained a mean score of 81.70 (68.08%). It indicates high level of Subjective Well-being among the total sample and various sample groups. The mean scores of all the groups vary among themselves and the same trend is visible in most of dimensions of Subjective Well-being of total sample and their sub groups. Only two dimensions of Subjective Well-being of the college teachers are having an average level of Subjective Well-being, they are Coping and Health.

The hypothesis that the level of Subjective well-being will vary among various sample groups is accepted here.

Table 3

Levels of Subjective Well-being of Various Sample Groups (N=100)

Dimensions	M	%	F	%	ST	%	CT	%	Total
HA	26.94	74.83	26.42	73.39	28.34	78.72	25.02	69.5	26.68
CO	17.66	73.58	16.62	69.25	18.64	77.66	15.64	65.17	17.14
OP	16.00	76.19	15.64	74.48	16.46	78.38	15.18	72.28	15.82
HE	14.14	78.55	12.14	67.44	14.50	80.55	11.78	65.44	13.15
SS	15.34	73.05	15.46	73.62	16.72	79.61	14.08	67.05	15.4
Total	90.08	75.06	86.28	71.9	94.66	78.88	81.70	68.08	88.18

HA- Happiness, CO- Coping, OP- Optimism, SS- Social Satisfaction, M- Male, F- Female, ST- School Teachers, CT- College Teachers

Comparison between Male and Female Teachers on Subjective Well-being

The study also aimed to see the difference in Subjective Well-being of male and female teachers. The mean score of male and female teachers on Subjective Well-being and on its dimensions have been presented in Table 4. Male teachers have obtained a score of 90.08 and females have obtained a mean score of 86.28 on total Subjective Well-being. The t-ratio of these two means is 1.82 which is not statistically significant. It indicates that there is no significant difference between male and female teacher on Subjective Well-being But, the level of Subjective Well-being of male teachers (90.08) is a little higher than that of female (86.28).

The hypothesis that there will be significant difference between male and female teachers on Subjective Well-being is rejected here.

Table 4

Comparison between Male and Female Teachers on Subjective Well-being (N-Male-50, Female-50)

Sample Groups	Mean	SD
Male	90.08	9.71
Female	86.28	11.06
t-ratio		1.82 ^{NS}

NS: Not significant

Comparison between School and College Teachers on Subjective Well-being

The mean score of school and college teachers on Subjective Well-being has been presented in Table 5. School teachers have obtained a mean score of 94.66 and their counterpart the college teachers have obtained a mean score of 80.7. The school teachers have scored more than the college teachers. The t-ratio of these two means is 6.99, which is significant at 0.01 level. It indicates that school and college teachers differ significantly on Subjective Well-being.

The hypothesis that there will be significant difference between school teachers and college teachers on Subjective Well-being is accepted here.

Table 5

Comparison between School and College Teachers on Subjective Well-being (N-School Teachers-50, College Teachers-50)

Sample Groups	Mean	SD
School Teachers	94.66	9.47
College Teachers	81.7	6.97
t-ratio		7.79*

**-Significant at .01 level*

Impact of Gender and Institutional Affiliation of Subjective Well-being: The ANOVA Analysis

The ANOVA analysis presented in Table 6 shows the two way interactional impact of gender and Institutional Affiliation on Subjective Well-being.

It may be seen that the F value for gender is 5.469 which is significant at 0.05 level, indicating that gender has a significant impact on Subjective Well-being of the teacher.

The F value for institutional affiliation is 63.61 which is significant at 0.01 level, indicating that institutional affiliation has a highly significant impact on Subjective well-being of the teachers. It may be also said that institutional affiliation of the teachers is responsible for the variation in Subjective well-being.

As far as the two way interaction is concerned, it may be seen that the F value (1.173) indicates the interactional effect of gender and institutional affiliation on Subjective Well-being. It is not significant even at 0.05 level, which indicates that the Subjective well-being of teachers is not influenced by the gender and institutional affiliation both combined.

Thus, the hypotheses that there will be significant impact of gender and institutional affiliation on Subjective Well-being is rejected here.

Table 6

Impact of Gender and Institutional Affiliation of Subjective Well-being

Variables	'F' (ANOVA)	Significance level
Gender	5.469	.05
Institutional Affiliation	63.61	.01
Gender* Institutional Affiliation	1.173	NS

NS- Not significant

Main Conclusion

- Teachers have obtained a mean score of 88.18 on total Subjective Well-being. It indicated high level of Subjective Well-being among the teachers.
- The mean scores indicated high level of Subjective Well-being among the total sample and its various sample groups, but the mean scores varied among themselves, indicating different level of Subjective Well-being among various sample sub groups.
- There is no significant difference between the Subjective Well-being of male and female teachers. But, male teachers have a little more Subjective Well-being than the female teachers.
- There is significant difference between the Subjective Well-being of school and college teachers. However, school teachers have little more Subjective Well-being than the college teachers.
- The F value (1.173) indicates that the Subjective well-being of teachers is not influenced by the gender and institutional affiliation both combined, but gender and institutional affiliation effect Subjective Well-being separately.

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